

Rotor Cage Assessment in Soft-Started Induction Motors Applying DWT and Hilbert Transform to Transient Stray Flux Signals

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Abstract— The identification of the fault-related signatures, caused by the presence of fault harmonics in the electrical signals, is quite more difficult in soft-started motors than in line-started ones. This is not only because of the higher harmonic content introduced by soft-starters, but also because of the amplification of certain components already present in line-fed motors. This work proposes a methodology that allows to enhance the identification of the rotor-fault-related components in soft-started induction motors. This methodology relies on the obtention of the envelope of the start-up stray-flux signals through the Hilbert transform. Then, the Discrete Wavelet Transform (DWT) is applied to the resulting envelope signals. This proposed method, unlike other methodologies, allows to clearly see the rotor-fault-related signatures when using different models of soft-starter and in different operating conditions. Additionally, an indicator to quantify the severity level of the failure is introduced. The results shown in this paper confirm the potential of this approach, even when different topologies of soft-starter and operating conditions are used.

Keywords— *induction motor; DWT; stray-flux; fault diagnosis; soft-starters; broken rotor bars.*

I. INTRODUCTION

In the latest years, the use of soft-starters as a way to start induction motors in industrial applications is increasing. The reason why this happens relies on the main function of these devices, which is to limit the high currents demanded by the induction motors during their startup. These currents can affect negatively both to the installations (unexpected tripping of protections, high drops of voltage, ...) and to the motors themselves (stresses on many motor parts, high thermal gradients on the insulation, ...) [1]. Soft-starters allow to damp the startup currents controlling the increasement of the RMS-value of the voltage supplied to the driven motor. That is what is called the voltage ramp. This control is usually done through a power electronics block, based on a set of thyristors. The typical configuration of those thyristors is in antiparallel and

can be installed in series with one, two or the three supply phases of the controlled motor [2].

Although the use of soft-starters yields many benefits there are, however, some disadvantages derived from it. One of them is related to the high harmonic content introduced by these devices in the motor current signals. In [2], [3], the authors proved that the amplitudes of some winding harmonics (WH) presented an increment in soft-started motors compared to line-started ones. In those works, also was demonstrated that the same happened to some principal slot harmonics (PSH). This fact makes the fault diagnosis process more difficult when applying techniques that rely on the analysis of motor currents. Although it was proven that some faults, such as rotor damages, still yield characteristic signatures in soft-started motors when analyzing their current signals with proper signal processing tools, their identification is far more difficult than in line-started motors. This also happens when the analyzed magnitude is the stray-flux. In [4], the authors proved that the analysis of stray-flux signals during the starting by applying suitable time-frequency tools, is a powerful source of information for detecting some kinds of faults in soft-started motors (including rotor damages). However, as it also happens when analyzing the transient currents, the harmonic content introduced by the soft-starter makes it difficult to identify the evolutions of some of the fault-related harmonics in the time-frequency maps obtained when applying the abovementioned time-frequency tools. Consequently, the development of methodologies able to obtain clearer signatures is of paramount interest, as it could lead to an easier identification of the fault-related patterns not only by experts, but also by automatic diagnosis systems.

Taking into account all the previous considerations, this work proposes a method to detect rotor damages in soft-started induction motors. This method enhances the identification of the patterns related to the rotor faults studied in this work. The approach relies on the obtention of the envelope of the startup stray-flux signals applying the Hilbert transform. Then, the Discrete Wavelet Transform is applied to the resulting envelope signal, obtaining its time-frequency decomposition. The fault-related patterns arising in the resulting time-frequency decomposition, allow to determine the health state of the rotor. Moreover, fault severity indicators can be defined. They relate the energy of the original signal with the energy of the DWT signal containing most of the fault

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component evolution. The methodology was validated in the laboratory using four different models of soft-starters of different manufacturers. In all the cases, very good results concerning both the detection of the considered faults and the determinations of the fault severity were obtained.

In this work, first the proposed methodology is introduced. Then, the experiments carried out to validate that methodology are explained and finally, the obtained results and the conclusions are exposed.

II. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

The analysis of the envelope of the signal of certain electrical quantities, has been used in several works. Particularly, the Hilbert Transform (HT) has been used as a way to better detect some specific components. As an example, in [5] the authors proposed the use of the HT to detect the presence of rotor faults in induction motors, when operating in reduced slip conditions. That was because when the fault-related components are close to the fundamental, them both may almost overlap and using the HT, makes it easier to extract the fault-related components.

The aim of obtaining the HT of a real signal $x(t)$, the stray-flux signal in this case, is emphasizing the local properties of that signal. Mathematically, the HT is given by (1) and defined as the convolution of the studied signal $x(t)$, with the function $1/\pi \cdot t$ [5], [6]. Actually, the HT is properly defined as the Cauchy principal value of the integral in (1), whenever this value exists [6].

$$HT(x(t)) = y(t) = \frac{1}{\pi \cdot t} \times x(t) = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{x(\tau)}{t-\tau} d\tau \quad (1)$$

One key property of the HT is that, as stated in [5], the HT of a trigonometric function $x(t)$ is a version of itself, but with the phase shifted 90° . Moreover, the amplitudes and frequencies of the spectrum of a Hilbert transformed series, are the same as the ones in the original data. The only difference is that the phase of each frequency component, is shifted by 90° [5].

On the other hand, in order to analyze the startup transient of the stray-flux signal, a time-frequency tool must be used. These tools are also known as Time-Frequency Decomposition tools (TFD). Although in previous works the selected TFD tool was the Short Time Fourier Transform (STFT) [7], in this study, the Discrete Wavelet Transform (DWT) is the TFD tool applied. This is due to its simplicity, the easy interpretation of the results, the possibility of obtaining indicators of the severity of the fault and last, but not least, its low computation requirements [2]. This latest characteristic could lead to an easier implementation of the proposed methodology in future automatic fault detection systems.

As a shallow explanation, the n -level DWT of a sampled signal performs a decomposition of that signal in a set of wavelet signals, which is composed of an approximation signal a_n and a set of detail signals d_1, d_2, \dots, d_n [8]. Each wavelet signal is associated to a frequency band, defined by the sampling rate of the original signal and the level of the wavelet signal. Each wavelet signal contains the time evolution of the frequency components which are included in the associated frequency band.

Taking advantage of the characteristics of both the HT and the DWT, this work proposes a methodology to facilitate the detection of the evolutions of some fault-related stray-flux components, otherwise not easily detectable when analyzing the stray-flux raw signal. The procedure of the proposed methodology is shown in Fig.1. In brief, it relies on applying first the HT to the stray-flux signal captured by means of the coil sensor. Then the DWT is applied to the resulting signal, obtaining its decomposition and thus identifying the fault related patterns. For this study, the DWT was applied using 10 decomposition levels and *dmeyer* as the mother wavelet. Finally, the fault severity indicators are computed. These indicators relate the energy of the original signal (the HT of the stray-flux signal in this case (H)) with the energy of the DWT signal containing most of the fault component evolution (d). That means that the higher the value of the indicator is, the healthier is the machine [2]. Mathematically, these indicators are given by (2):

$$\gamma_{DE}(dB) = 10 \cdot \log \left[\frac{\sum_{j=Nb}^{Ns} H_j^2}{\sum_{j=Nb}^{Ns} [d_{nf+1}(j)]^2} \right] \quad (2)$$

Fig. 1. Schematic block diagram of the proposed methodology.

III. EXPERIMENTS

For this study, several tests were carried out at the laboratory using a testbench. That testbench consisted of a 4P, 400V, 1.1kW squirrel cage induction motor (SCIM), coupled to a DC motor acting as a load. In order to set different levels of load, the excitation current of the DC motor was modified. In the experiments, the tested SCIM was started using four different models of soft-starter, all of them from well-known

manufacturers. In order to keep the privacy of the results, the models are not identified to the brand name in this paper. On the contrary, they are denoted as Model A, B, C and D (see Fig.2(b)). These models had different topologies and controlled different supply phases (one, two or three depending on the model). Additionally, the proposed methodology was tested using rotors with three different fault severities, namely healthy state, one broken bar and two broken bars. To carry out each test, the SCIM was started using the corresponding soft-starter. For each model of soft-starter, different combinations of voltage ramp duration and initial voltage were set. During the startups, the stray-flux was captured by means of a self-manufactured coil sensor attached to the frame of the SCIM (see Fig.2(a)) and recorded with an oscilloscope. That sensor had 1,000 turns, being the wire diameter 0,2mm, the external diameter 8cm and the internal diameter 3.9cm. The recorded stray-flux signals were then transferred to a PC where they were analyzed applying the proposed methodology.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 2. (a) Experimental testbench, (b) Models of soft-starter used in the tests.

TABLE I. MAIN CHARACTERISTICS OF THE USED SOFT-STARTERS

	Model A	Model B	Model C	Model D
Rated voltage (V)	380-400	380-400	400	380-400
Rated power (kW)	1.5	2.2	4	1.5
Maximum current (A)	3.6	5.5	9	3.9
Rated frequency (Hz)	50	50	50	50
Controlled phases	R-T	R-S-T	R	R-S
Voltage ramp duration (s)	0-20	1-25	1-5	1-20

IV. RESULTS

Fig. 3(a) and (b), show a comparative of the DWT of the HT and of the raw stray-flux signals, for the three different health states of the rotor (healthy, 1 broken bar and 2 broken bars). These results, correspond only to two of the models of soft-starter. Although many different tests were developed, only some representative cases are shown due to space limitations. For all the other cases and models of soft-starter, the results are similar.

In Fig.3 (a) and (b), the differences between the DWT of the raw signal and the DWT of the HT are evident. Although in the case of the DWT of the raw signals no fault-related pattern (V-shaped for the $f \cdot (1 - 2 \cdot s)$ component or ascending trend for the $s \cdot f$ component) arises neither in the case of 1 broken bar nor in the case of 2 broken bars, when the DWT is applied to the HT of the stray-flux signals, the fault-related patterns are evident. These fault patterns for the HT, correspond to the $s \cdot f$ component (where s is the slip and f is the supply frequency), that is linked with rotor damages. The evolution of this component in the time-frequency maps when the STFT is applied, as defined in [7], rises from 0Hz to almost the supply frequency (50Hz in this case). This corresponds to the typical evolution of this component when the raw signal is studied (from 50Hz to almost 0Hz), but shifted 90° due to the application of the HT. In the decomposition obtained when applying the DWT, since the higher levels of detail correspond to the lower values of frequency, this pattern should appear as a descending trend from the highest level of detail to the lower ones. And this is what can be seen in the results shown in Fig.3 (a) and (b). While in the healthy state no evident fault-related pattern can be seen, in the case of one broken bar and two broken bars the expected pattern clearly shows up. The trend of this pattern is tracked with blue arrows in Fig.3 (a) and (b).

On the other hand, Table II shows the value of the fault severity indicator γ_{ED} , defined in a previous section, for all the models of soft-starter and for all the rotor health states. It is noticeable that, for every model, the indicator clearly decreases its value as the fault worsens. That decrement is significant for all the models, proving the reliability of the proposed indicator for determining the severity of the rotor fault in soft-started induction motors.

TABLE II. VALUES OF THE PROPOSED FAULT SEVERITY INDICATOR γ_{DE} FOR EACH MODEL OF SOFT-STARTER AND ROTOR HEALTH STATE.

	Healthy	1 broken bar	2 broken bars
Model A	34.2319	27.1528 (- 20.7%)	22.9150 (- 33%)
Model B	35.4193	26.8772 (- 24.1%)	20.4987 (- 42.1%)
Model C	31.3659	26.1000 (- 16.8%)	16.8983 (- 46.1%)
Model D	37.1518	29.8032 (- 19.8%)	16.1213 (- 56.6%)

In summary, the presence of the $s \cdot f$ component clearly indicates the presence of a rotor fault. On the other hand, the computation of the proposed indicator allows to determine the severity of the failure. Thus, this method allows to easily detect not only if the studied rotor has a broken bar, but also to categorize the severity of the fault.

Fig. 3. (a) Results for soft-starter model A, (b) Results for soft-starter model B

V. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, a new methodology for the assessment of the rotor condition in soft-started induction motors is proposed. The methodology relies on the obtention of the envelope of the stray-flux startup signal via the Hilbert transform. Then, the DWT is applied to it in order to track the characteristic evolution of the fault-related components. Compared to the application of the DWT to the raw signal, this new methodology gives clearer results, making the identification of the fault signatures easier both by experts and by automatic pattern-recognition algorithms. Besides, fault severity

indicators have been defined in this work, showing high consistency for the determination of the level of the rotor failure for all the considered soft-starter models.

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